

Understanding Parental Factors and Entrepreneurial Attitude - The Moderating Effect of Entrepreneurship

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Abstract

Entrepreneurs are individuals who take calculated risks, delve into ventures by organizing the factors of production in a way to get economic value from the resources, and are willing to bear the eventful loss that may arise from the investment. The entrepreneurs have self-motivation as well as self-determination traits that come a long way from the initial social agents that are in the life of the individual affecting how and whether they will have the entrepreneurial intent. The entrepreneurial intent is primarily subject to the influence of the parents a higher degree of the influence for a male child being from a family with both parents pursuing self-employment and a lower degree for the female child with self- employed parents. Regarding the career path one takes, the influencers are the parents specifically a father having a greater influence for the male child, and the female child influenced greatly by the mother then the teachers in a smaller scale.

Keyword: *Entrepreneurial Attitude, Career Choice, Entrepreneurial Intention, parents, family roles, career guidance*

Research Framework

In this research, we would like to investigate the correlation of an individual inclined towards pursuing entrepreneurship and the background of the individual whether male or female. The background will entail the initial social interaction of the individual from a family set up to the time when one makes the actual decision to pursue entrepreneurship or any other career path. All these factors affect how an individual will respond to their desire to pursue entrepreneurship or shun entrepreneurship.

Introduction

An entrepreneur is an innovative person willing to take a risk, recognizing the possibility of failure and reorganizes available resources passionately and confidently with the aim of creating value from the endeavor (Rachmawan, Ayu, &Wustari 419). An entrepreneur, therefore, is pertinent to economic development as they help steer the economy in directions initially unnoticeable to the mass. Entrepreneurs notice opportunities in the market, calculate and take the risk, deriving economic value from the opportunity hence economic development. The entrepreneurial attitude, as a lifestyle in itself, comes from various factors that the entrepreneur affiliates to while their shape depends on time from interaction with parents to life circumstances that shape an individual.

Entrepreneurial Intention

The parent's careers tend to affect entrepreneurial intention and even from the initial stages in the entrepreneur's life, and this applies differently to the gender of the entrepreneur. In particular, this is because parents are the first agents for socializing; the parents end up shaping the individuals' entrepreneurial orientation.

For instance, if both parents are under self-employment, it affects the entrepreneurial intention of the male children differently from the female children. Ideally, this is because the male children will incline to pursue self-employment, unlike the female child. On the other hand, the female child will tend to pursue self-employment in the scenario where only one parent is pursuing self-employment (Polin, Chaim, & Avi 268).

TABLE 1. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF SELF-EFFICACY, PARENT'S INFLUENCE, AND ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION

Variables	N	%	Self-Efficacy			Parent's influence			Entrepreneurial Intention		
			Mean	SD	Sign	Mean	SD	Sign	Mean	SD	Sign
Sex/Gender											
Male	90	42	4.140	0.432	0.521	3.503	0.834	0.453	5.182	0.804	0.422
Female	125	57	4.078	0.467		3.667	0.763		5.055	0.781	
Ethnicity											
Javanese	82	38	4.090	0.466	0.581	3.643	0.745	0.105	5.080	0.832	0.937
Sundanese	70	33	4.111	0.440		3.496	0.937		5.112	0.764	
Betawi	10	5	4.100	0.413		3.875	0.637		5.011	0.817	
Mixed	28	13	4.214	0.501		3.839	0.616		5.111	0.753	
Others	25	12	4.008	0.402		3.350	0.680		5.227	0.808	
Living with											
Parents	156	73	4.079	0.424	0.607	3.693	0.795	0.039*	5.121	0.760	0.299
Family/Relatives	9	42	4.222	0.560		3.527	0.578		5.344	0.807	
Students Dorm	19	9	4.168	0.438		3.105	0.859		5.241	0.870	
Others	31	14	4.158	0.562		3.642	0.735		4.892	0.877	
Father's Occ											
Entrepreneur	43	20	4.172	0.513	0.643	3.476	0.837	0.399	5.096	0.920	0.414
Public Servant	83	39	4.062	0.456		3.656	0.820		5.014	0.748	
Private Sector	52	24	4.088	0.414		3.673	0.701		5.167	0.796	
Teacher/Lecturer	14	7	4.085	0.310		3.410	0.601		5.505	0.602	
Med Doctor	7	3	4.057	0.457		3.964	0.443		5.102	0.463	
Military	12	6	4.150	0.468		3.479	0.869		4.971	0.900	
Farmer	4	2	4.450	0.597		3.062	1.599		5.457	0.661	
Mother's Occ											
Entrepreneur	15	7	4.173	0.281	0.781	3.317	0.753	0.01*	5.673	0.790	0.477
Public Servant	49	23	4.110	0.496		3.842	0.657		4.987	0.673	
Private Sector	10	5	4.240	0.556		3.175	0.951		4.867	0.768	
Teacher/Lecturer	21	10	4.076	0.527		3.071	0.780		4.990	0.755	
Farmer	2	0.9	4.400	0.283		4.000	0.354		5.530	0.905	
Housewife	118	55	4.081	0.433		3.655	0.796		5.173	0.843	
Experience											
Yes	96	45	4.131	0.464	0.392	3.568	0.841	0.660	5.491	0.688	0.000*
No	11	5	4.078	0.445		3.616	0.766		4.772	0.717	

* Significant at l.o.s. $p < 0.05$

(Rachmawan, Ayu, and Wustari 425)

Much as the entrepreneurial intention of males and females differ, the entrepreneurial intention for the male is higher than that of the female, that of children with entrepreneurial parents higher than children who do not have entrepreneurial parents. Even more, the entrepreneurial intention is higher in homes that there are a

large number of entrepreneurial role models in comparison to families with no entrepreneurial role models (Polin, Chaim, & Avi 269).

Gender and Parental Impact

The entrepreneurial intention of the male and the female children in a family differs from that of the male being high. Consequently, this even escalates in instances where both parents are entrepreneurs and are pursuing self-employment. When it comes to career choices, the father and the female child by the mother influence the male child. This influence on the career is a witness from the teachers as they interact with the children, they take the secondary role of influence, and parents take the primary role (Polin, Chaim, & Avi 270).

Regarding entrepreneurship, a male child has a high inclination of influence from a self-employed mother in comparison to a self-employed father. For a female child, the female highly inclines to the influence a self-employed mother than a self-employed father except for the circumstance where both parents are pursuing self-employment; the entrepreneurial intention for the female is low (Polin, Chaim, & Avi 280).

Table 2: Entrepreneurial intention based on parental employment divided into 5 combined for both males and females (Polin, Chaim, & Avi 275).

Career Choice

The choice of a career that one takes whether to venture into self-employment or whether to choose a career as an employee depends on some factors. The influence stems from their surrounding with parents being key to the degree of influence than teachers. The inclination of the influence of the father on a man as well as the influence of the mother on a woman in matters concerning marriage and career are major because of the perception that each one is a respective role model for the child (Polin, Chaim, & Avi 270).

As to whether one chooses a career path, or whether one chooses entrepreneurship, is a question of one's choice to commit to the career objective (Ilouga, Nyock, & Sahut 717). As a result, this means that an individual will commit to a career path that they are willing to shoulder. An entrepreneur must be willing to take the risk despite the challenges and economic constraints, willingness to persevere in the process of entrepreneurship as well as have the skills to do that and have self-motivation. These factors will affect the willingness of one committing to an entrepreneurial career (Ilouga, Nyock, & Sahut 726). Therefore, career-oriented individuals will be unwilling to bear all uncertainty and lack the drive required such as self-motivation and self-determination, which are necessary for an entrepreneur.

Life Experience and Entrepreneurship

Figure 1: Life experience and entrepreneurship (Rachmawan, Ayu, and Wustari 421).

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship is key to the development of an economy. The entrepreneurial intention, however, is also key to determining the number of entrepreneur vis-à-vis the number of people who will opt for formal employment. The entrepreneurial intention is a key factor that determines entrepreneurs, and it features from the initial stages of an individual interaction or socializing agents. Parents are the primary socializing agents of an individual and their inclination to entrepreneurship and being self-employed affects their children's entrepreneurial intention differently with the overall entrepreneurial intention for the male children being higher than that of the female children.

Parents affect the career path that a child takes, with fathers mainly influencing male children and the female children influenced by their mothers. In addition, the teachers place a third-degree role in influencing the career of the children. However, as to whether one takes up an entrepreneurial or employment path, is volitional and one's ability to display the entrepreneurial traits.

Finally, the parents play a crucial role in influencing the perception of the children on entrepreneurship and the operation of businesses. Therefore, parents should guide their children in cultivating the entrepreneurial spirit to advance economic growth through innovations and creation of employment in the society. The early stages of a child highly influence the entrepreneurial path of the child.

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